

RESEARCH ORIENTED TEACHING METHODOLOGY – AN APPROACH FOR EXCELLENCE IN THE SYSTEM OF CONTINUOUS EDUCATION

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Abstract. *The present article describes an approach for excellence in teaching exact and natural sciences through research-oriented teaching methodology. The ever-developing technology requires students with intellectual and creative thinking. According to the needs of the society, the students should be motivated to apply the basic knowledge of exact and natural sciences to solve the unsolved problems in science and technology thereby creating a well advanced and more sophisticated society with high security. The traditional methods of teaching exact and natural sciences are inadequate to reach the latest technologies and hence there is a need to search for a well-organized and highly structured advanced teaching methods. One of the best practices is the research-oriented teaching methodology for secondary and higher secondary school students along with the use of IT tools in the class room.*

Introduction

Education affords the transmission of the values and accumulated knowledge of civilization. Education is the only system that guides the people in learning the culture along with the contribution in the ever-developing technology that helps the future generation. The basic knowledge of exact and natural sciences is applied in every latest technology and creating miracles and solving so many unsolved problems in nature. The natural phenomenon occurring in the universe such as sudden raising of temperatures over a region, Ozone depletion, heavy Earthquakes, heavy rainfalls over certain regions and the artificial phenomenon such as artificial radioactivity, generation of nuclear power, artificially intelligent machines etc., are posing challenges to the young generation. The students of this generation are physically and psychologically strong enough and self-motivated to face the challenges and are fast learners. Few technologies which are more accurate in teaching such as robotic teaching technique, chat GPT techniques and online teaching methods are widely used now a days but finds limited use only. The major drawback of this new technology is the lack of continuous monitoring of the student. The traditional method of black board teaching is inadequate but mandatory in school studies as every student were monitored and continuous observation is necessary for understanding the field of interests of the student and guide the students towards achieving the goals. Hence, there should be a compromise in teaching-learning process between traditional and modern teaching methodologies. Now a days the students are not showing interest towards the theory classes and are unable to spend more time in studies and traditional ways of learning processes. For every concept, there should be some scientific validation and also application oriented. Hence, it is the

prime responsibility of the teachers to motivate the students towards their goals with the aid of modern teaching methods. In this regard, researchers and Philosophers are trying to bring the best teaching-learning practices in the fields of science and technology right from the school level.

Research oriented teaching methodology

Research oriented teaching methodology is one of the best practices to achieve excellence in teaching exact and natural sciences in the system of continuous education. In Research-oriented teaching methodology, teachers will address the problem to the student and guide the student to search for the solution through exploration, think, critically evaluate, and apply knowledge to solve the problem (1). Since few decades, European countries are following this trend of teaching and succeeded by making their students more innovative and critical thinkers rather than passive listeners.

Research-oriented teaching methodology involves observation, question, hypothesis, aims, method, results (data and analysis), discussion, and conclusion (2), problem solving, independent research and projects (3), active teaching (4), problem-based learning (5), service learning, project method, interactive learning (6), cooperative learning etc., A statistical survey reported student's performance was affected in a positive manner by teacher's research-oriented teaching methodology (7). Research-oriented teaching methods elucidates the existing knowledge and create new knowledge. The simple way of understanding the research-oriented teaching method is to demonstrate the students that the phenomenon related to natural and exact sciences as a problem and the students has to search for the solution through various channels such as library, online etc., The role of teacher is to mentor the student and guide the student in collecting the information and analysis of the information. During the analysis part, the students sometimes face difficulties and there need of the teacher comes into existence. The teacher has to support morally instead of explaining the step-by-step process in finding the solution. After analyzing the information, the student has to conclude. The role of teacher is to check the results whether the work is original, ecofriendly, authenticity, usefulness to the society etc.,

In order to guide a student properly the basic requirement of the teacher is to have sufficient knowledge in that field of interest. The teacher should be updated in latest research findings and should act as a knowledge hub. The complete future of the student lies in the hands of the teacher. If the teacher guides from the earliest age of the student with a proper idea of finding new things in exact and natural sciences, the student can get awareness in which filed he needs to improve his own skills. According to the needs, the student will plan his own ideas and the way of learning the concepts. In research-oriented teaching methodology, the student will be given a task by the teacher and the student is asked to find the solution of the problem. The student has to search the books or online resources to get a clear picture of the task (The task should be like a problem of some phenomenon in exact and natural sciences) and has to find a way to solve the problem. During the search process, the teacher has to guide the student about the resources only to find the solution but should not provide the detailed solution. After finding the solution, the student will approach the teacher and tries to explain the solution to the given problem. The teacher has to guide the student towards writing the report of the findings and then it is the responsibility of the teacher to check the authenticity of the results. If the teacher finds any misconceptions or mistakes in the report, it should be reviewed properly until the solution is authenticated. The final stage of the process is the validation by the teacher followed by the future scope of the present study. Most of the times, the students have to spend in the library and laboratories. There are so many countries such as US and UK where the students are trained towards doing project works during the school

hours rather than listening the classes as in the traditional teaching methodology using black boards. It is the prime responsibility of the Governments to provide sophisticated laboratory facility, library in the Government schools and also to establish Regional National Science centers across the country. The minor project works should be carried out by the students in the school campus and major projects should be guided by the teacher using the national science centers. After completion of the project works, the students should give a seminar to all the teachers in the school and should share the knowledge with the other students. Through the discussions, the students will gain sufficient knowledge and also, they will learn to work as a team in a collaborative way which is called collaborative research in scientific terminology. With these inclusions along with the black board traditional teaching, the results are exclusive and the students were succeeded and competitive in the ever-developing technology.

Conclusion

With the advances in technology, the traditional ways of teaching are inadequate. There is a need for searching innovative teaching methodologies which provides a fruitful learning environment for the students. Research oriented teaching methodology is one of the methodologies where the students can learn the scientific theories through practice and minor project works. The role of teacher in the research-oriented teaching methodology is exclusive and the teacher need to guide the students rather than teaching in the class room. In well developed countries such as US and UK, better results were reported through the research-oriented teaching methodology. Through this teaching method the students become active listeners with more practical knowledge and innovative skills.

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